

The Use of New Technologies in Education: Some Proposals on Designing an Entrepreneurship Course Using Second Life®

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Abstract — The use of new technologies can enhance learning, but we need to know how to use them and in what contexts. In this paper we will describe the design of an Entrepreneurship Course, in which the use of Second Life, a 3D Virtual World and Moodle, a Learning Management System are mandatory. We will describe a first approach on the using new technologies that can add value to the learning process and that can open possibilities that face-to-face classes does not offer anymore.

Index Terms — Active Learning, e-Learning, Entrepreneurship, Second Life

1 INTRODUCTION

Every medium has a specific language, a specific way of transmitting information. A radio program will not work on television, although it is technically possible to transmit it that way. When a new medium appears, we tend to use the language of the media we already know. We have several examples through media History. Early television was made in a radio's language form, early cinema was made through theatre language. "We impose the form of the old on the content of the new." [1]

This kind of evolution happens in what we call new technologies in general and in education specific technology.

In the early days of the World Wide Web it was easy to find web pages full of text with a big scrollbar, until research showed that we do not read on the screen the same way we read on paper. In the early days of e-Learning, it was common to transfer the face-to-face classroom techniques of teaching to online distance education. It is only when we start to understand the specific language of the new medium that we can explore it in its full potential.

One common example of this problem we observe is the use of a new technology in education because of the hype around it. It is not uncommon to see Universities gaining space in traditional media, like newspapers and television, because they started to use the last technology. Most of the times this reason to the use of the technology in education will conduct to the rejection of the technology by teachers and students, because in some cases technology is not adding value, only more work and time spent on the process. New technologies do not solve education problems, they are just tools. It is the way they are used that adds value to learning and the participants of the learning process, students and teachers, need to be aware of the value added by the news ways of learning and teaching.

Another aspect we need to take into account is the fact that the students' profile is changing. Today's students are more comfortable with technology, incorporating it in an active way in their lives. Traditional education techniques will not work with these students, as "The Horizon report" states "Students' views of what is and what is not technology are increasingly different from those of faculty. From small, flexible software tools to ubiquitous portables devices and instant access, students' today experience technology very differently that faculty do, and the gap between student's view of technology and that of faculty is growing rapidly." [2] One possible way to gain the new kind of student into the learning process is to find out how to teach them with tools familiar to them, like

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games, instant messenger, virtual worlds, etc.

This paper will describe the design of a course about entrepreneurship, that requires the use of Second Life (<http://secondlife.com>), a 3D Virtual World, and Moodle (<http://moodle.org>), a Learning Management System, according to their own language.

Usually, the use of new technologies, in education, start with experimentation. We believe that, at this point, there are several examples of its use, so we decided to gather the best practices that would benefit our course.

This paper is a result of that research and it presents a possible guide structure to the design of the Entrepreneurship Course to be lectured next academic year. At the end of the course we will evaluate it and compare the results with this first guide, in order to understand the positive or negative results and how to make it better.

In this paper, we will explain why we chose Second Life and Moodle as tools to our course. We will start from a general structure of an entrepreneurship course to describe in which sections we will use each technology and why. We will focus in Socialization, as a mandatory step in this kind of education, and in "Real Learning", where we will emphasize in which sections the technology is adding value to the process.

We will finish this paper by reflecting on the roles of the actors of the learning and teaching process, as we think changes are required.

2 DESIGNING AN ENTREPRENEURSHIP COURSE – THE STRUCTURE

Second Life is a 3D Virtual World created by its residents. Everyone can register for a free account, which gives them an avatar, a physical representation of the user called resident, which can move, walk and fly in the world. Residents can own land and they can build everything they want there, houses, clothes, gardens, etc. The limits are the knowledge of the technology and imagination of the user.

Second Life has an economy based on Linden Dollars that can be transformed in US Dollars and vice-versa. Residents can buy and sell land and objects in the Virtual World to other residents.

Entrepreneurship is not a strange concept in Second Life. In fact, there are many examples, through web, of people starting their businesses in Second Life. Last year, The Electric Sheep Company and Eldman

have announced a SL Business Plan Contest¹ and in October of 2007, Wiley Publishing, Inc. have published Daniel Terdiman's book² "The Entrepreneur's Guide to Second Life: Making Money in the Metaverse" [3]

Second Life promotes active learning among its residents, as pointed out by Ondrejka, "the power of virtual worlds to convey information, and potentially to reduce the cost of learning within them due to pervasive connectivity and social networks, means the same technologies and techniques that apply to education also lead to changes in business process and entrepreneurship. Combined with the far lower capital expenses inherent in digital worlds, in Second Life hundreds of thousands of residents try out new roles, learn new skills, and approach learning with a passion and excitement they may not have possessed in school." [4]

The Entrepreneurship Course, to be lectured next year, aims to provide competencies to students about innovation and enterprise management, which will enable them to develop and execute a business idea. The students will be integrated in a process of business creation, according to the following sections:

1. News Section – Notifications about meetings and changes during the course.
2. Presentation – Information about the course.
3. Introduction – Students will be introduced to the technology used during the course.
4. Idea – Discussion of business' ideas.
5. Team – How to develop a good team, roles of team members.
6. Ethic and Legal Issues – Questions regarding registering the business.
7. Investment – Types of investment, Government aids, angel investors, etc.
8. Market – Identification of market opportunities, marketing strategies and sales.
9. Business Plan – How to make a good business plan.
10. Business Creation.
11. Evaluation.

One of the best ways of teaching a subject is to give students the opportunity to practice it, which also enhances their motivation. Yet, the execution of a business idea has risks and

¹<http://www.electricsheepcompany.com/core/about/announcements/?NewsAction=renderById&NewsId=12>

²<http://entrepreneursguidetosecondlife.blogspot.com>

costs that can not be supported in a learning process. This is why we will make use of Moodle, a Learning Management System, and Second Life, a 3D Virtual World. Each of these two technologies will have a specific function in the course.

The Entrepreneurship Course will be designed in Moodle, which can be used as a platform to gather documents and display the syllabus of the course. In an e-Learning course the student must have access to the complete structure of the learning process, from the beginning to the end, before the course itself starts.

Moodle will include eleven sections. The first section will have a news forum and a chat system, where students will be notified about news, meetings in Second Life or changes during the course. The student can be notified through email each time something is posted in this section.

The second section will welcome and encourage the students as well as have information about the structure of the course, the time it will last, the learning outcomes expected, and the information about teachers and institutions involved in the course.

3 THE IMPORTANCE OF SOCIALIZATION

The third section, named Introduction, will have simple tasks to the student like filling in their profile in Moodle, creating their avatar and customizing its appearance in Second Life. The teacher or the tutor will promote at this stage a discussion on Second Life between students, in which they will present themselves and will talk about their motivations and expectations to take the course.

Although many teachers would like to step out of this level and start the "real learning" right away, it is very important that they spend a reasonable time promoting socialization between students, since this could determine the successful participation in a cohesive learning community later on, as pointed out by Gilly Salmon [5]. As stated by Terry Anderson [6], "the first task of the e-learning teacher is to develop a sense of trust and safety within the electronic community. In the absence of this trust, learners will feel uncomfortable and constrained in posting their thoughts and comments. We usually facilitate this trust information by having students post a series of introductory comments about themselves". The use of Second Life, at this stage, will make easier, comparing with other systems of e-Learning like Moodle, the main goal of this section: establishing relationships between

students, which develop naturally in face-to-face classrooms, but it is more difficult to achieve in distance education. The possibility of the students to have a physical representation of their "selves" through the avatar, in Second Life, will make it easier for them to establish relationships with each other, as experienced by Rebecca Nesson, a Harvard Extension School instructor [7].

The students will have access, in this section in Moodle, to step-by-step documents that will enable them to get acquainted with the technologies used in the course.

At the end of this section, the students will know each other and will have a good knowledge of how the applications work.

4 THE "REAL LEARNING"

In this chapter we will describe in which sections of the course we will use each technology, explaining why. The fourth section of the course, the discussion of the business idea, will start the "real learning".

This step of the course will promote brainstorming and discussion between students about a possible business idea. At this stage, we can find some problems about student's participation. There is always the kind of student whom is very hard to bring to the discussion and there is another kind of student that dominates the discussion. Rebecca Nesson [7] found out that, in a text based chat in Second Life, the differences between the student that does not participate and that of the student that dominates the discussion are minimized or disappear. On one side, the anxiety of public-speaking aspect does not apply because the student feels no one is looking at him, it is just his avatar. On the other side, since we are talking about a text based participation, the student who usually has a very active participation does not interfere with other participations, since students can write at the same time.

For a brainstorming session, Second Life is much more than a simple real time chat system that provides communication between people physically away. Students will be more comfortable to share their ideas in a technology application that provides a context and an environment, which does not happen in another real time chat or video systems, like Jabber (<http://www.jabber.org/>) or Skype (<http://www.skype.com>) applications.

About the importance of the environment around communication, that Second Life provides, Kelton [8] states that "many of those involved in Second Life develop an attachment to their avatar, created from the

onset by extensive customization and a suspension of disbelief. Students seem more willing to buy into the learning experience because it feels "real" to them, certainly more engaging than a two-dimensional experience."

Educational experiences in Second Life have demonstrated that it is easier for the students to be evolved in a discussion in that kind of environment that in other systems like forums in Moodle[7], maybe because they have a representation of the "selves", as we pointed out previously.

Second Life has some limitations, though. It is very difficult to save the discussions to read later on, for example. At this point we will be using Sloodle (<http://sloodle.org>), a platform that provides communication between Second Life and Moodle. By registering the Second Life discussions on Moodle, students will be able to think again about what it was discussed previously.

The section about teams will also be explored in Second Life, since we are talking about communication and roles.

Sections concerning ethic and legal issues and types of investment will have more emphasis in Moodle, since the main function of these steps is to provide information about theoretical and bureaucracy aspects of creating a business. This will enable teachers to provide information about the differences between a business in Second Life and a business in real life.

At this stage, Second Life will be used to perform role-play activities. It is important to students to practice how they should communicate and convince investors of the potential of their ideas and businesses. Avatars can make movements and gestures, through scripts. Students will be able to learn how to convince investors by doing it in the Virtual World, through voice-chat and posture of the avatar. The simulated situation can be record, viewed and discussed afterwards. The teacher, then, can give some advice about what was right or failed in the situation of convincing an investor for a specific idea or product.

The eighth section of the Entrepreneurship Course is about Market and while it can have documentation on Moodle, its activities are in Second Life. There are many companies working on market studies, inside a virtual world. Students can have the possibility of running their own market studies, among the Second Life population and they can access several resources concerning market data, demographic studies or marketing white papers about real brands in Second Life through the Virtual World Wiki about Market at

<http://wiki.secondlife.com/wiki/Marketing>.

For the Business Plan section, we will be using Moodle for documentation and collaborative writing. Students will be asked to join in groups in the beginning of the course, so they will need an application, like a wiki, which is provided by Moodle, to write the business plan. After the Business Plan is completed, the students will be asked to present it on Second Life. It is very difficult to institutions to bring experts to a traditional classroom to talk to the students, because it would imply costs of travelling and housing. If the presentation of the business plan is made in a Virtual World it is easier to get experienced professionals to connect to Second Life and comment on the students work. This will add a greater motivation for students and they will be able to access to experts opinion. Virtual conferences in Second Life are gathering many adepts. Enterprises like Sun, IBM and Dell are making press and work conferences in the Virtual World. Many Real World conferences are being streamed to Second Life, in order to reach to different public. There are even companies which business is to setup conferences in Second Life, like Conference Island (<http://www.conferenceisland.com>). In the case of Entrepreneurship Course, the experts invited would need to install the Second Life client on their computers and register for an account, if they do not have one already.

The tenth section of the course will be the creation of the business on Second Life. Each group of students will have a small grant in Linden Dollars to begin with, which they can use to buy objects or pay to other fellow students, with competencies to do something they need to run their business. Students can trade objects, textures or services between groups. This way, we hope to promote collaboration and provide an environment where the students will act as they need to do in Real World, like having expenses and profits with their businesses. Students can explore the possibilities of running the business, by selling the products they created, which can be objects or services, to fellow students or to other residents of Second Life, by executing marketing techniques learned during the course.

The last section of the course will be evaluation, where we will present not only the students evaluation, but also evaluate the course itself by providing questionnaires to the students.

In the following table, we present a resume of the structure of the Entrepreneurship

Course:

TABLE 1
STRUCTURE OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP COURSE

Topics	Technology	Benefits
News Section	Moodle (forum)	Provides a place where students can be notified of changes of the course and meetings by email.
Presentation	Moodle (webpage)	Information about the structure of the course, learning outcomes expected and information and contacts of teachers and institutions.
Introduction	Second Life and Moodle	Socialization; learning about the technology
Idea	Second Life and Sloodle	Socialization; good environment for brainstorming; review of the sessions
Team	Second Life	Socialization; knowledge about students competencies and expectations
Ethic and Legal Issues	Moodle (webpages and forum)	Information; questions from the students
Investment	Moodle (webpage), Second Life and Sloodle	Information and role-play activities, review of the sessions
Market	Moodle (webpage) and Second Life	Information resources; market research in Virtual World
Business Plan	Moodle (wiki)	Collaborative writing
Business	Second Life	Creation, collaboration, active learning
Evaluation	Moodle (questionnaires)	Feedback from the students about the course.

5 THE ACTORS

When we think about using new technologies to education, we need to focus on the people involved. It is crucial that all the participants see that technology will add value to the process of learning. Most of the times we are talking about teachers and students that do not have much experience with technology.

Furthermore, they need to feel they are supported. Besides students and teachers it is important to have the support of a computer science expert and a tutor, a new emerging type of professional.

We define the tutor as a person who mediates between the computer science expert, which most of the times has other responsibilities in an educational institution, the teachers and the students. The role of the tutor is to design the course, according to the directions of the teacher, to create "how to's", step-by-step instructions which will guide students and teachers through registering and management processes in Moodle and in Second Life and to attend students and teachers questions regarding accessibility to the contents of the course. This will leave the teacher to the teaching process and students will feel they are being supported in technological aspects.

From our experience in two international master programs³ and several discussions with teachers beginning to use new technologies in Education, we have noticed that teachers need a special attention. The fact is that our students were born in a Technology Era, so they learned these media languages very easily as they were growing up. Teachers need to learn this whole new media language, with which they may feel uncomfortable, and apply it to education. Furthermore, teachers are overwhelmed with work, mostly administrative. The role of the tutor, a person who can easily move between education and new technologies, can be, in this case, crucial for the success of the course.

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper we described how we designed an Entrepreneurship Course, making use of new technologies. Our main goal was to reflect and to find a suitable way of using those technologies. Second Life has a great potential in Education. In our course, discussions, role-play activities and the construction of a business could not be made in a suitable way in a face-to-face classroom. With Moodle and Sloodle platforms, we can provide documentation and theoretical support to the students and teachers. Each of the technology used serve specific needs that

³"Roads to Democracy(es)", a Master Program between University of Coimbra, in Portugal and University of Uppsala, in Sweden and "EuroMACHS", a Master Program between University of Coimbra, in Portugal, University of Turku, in Finland, University of Cologne, in Germany and University of Lecce in Italy.

result on the learning outcomes expected. New technologies are growing faster and faster, students are changing according to their use of that technology and we need to try to understand their language, how they work and in what ways they can enhance education.

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